

Dynamic Hip Screw versus Proximal Femoral Nail in the Treatment of Stable Intertrochanteric Fractures

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The choice between dynamic hip screw (DHS) and proximal femoral nail (PFN) for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures of hip remains controversial. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of these two implants in terms of early mobility, complications and functional recovery.

Methods: A retrospective comparative study was conducted on 100 patients with stable intertrochanteric fractures (AO/OTA 31-A1) treated with either DHS (n=50) or PFN (n=50). Intraoperative, postoperative, radiographic, and functional outcomes were assessed. The minimum follow-up period was 12 months.

Results: The PFN group had significantly shorter surgical times (55.2 ± 10.8 min vs. 68.4 ± 12.5 min, $p < 0.001$), less blood loss (135.4 ± 38.7 mL vs. 180.6 ± 45.3 mL, $p < 0.001$), earlier mobility (2.5 ± 0.9 days vs. 3.8 ± 1.2 days, $p < 0.001$), better weight-bearing status at discharge (full: 48% vs. 20%, $p = 0.002$), and shorter hospital stays (6.8 ± 1.9 days vs. 8.5 ± 2.3 days, $p < 0.001$) compared to the DHS group. At 12 months, the PFN group had higher Harris Hip Scores (87.2 ± 5.9 vs. 84.6 ± 6.8 , $p = 0.042$) and Parker Mobility Scores (7.8 ± 1.3 vs. 7.2 ± 1.5 , $p = 0.033$). Complication rates were lower in the PFN group, but the differences were not statistically significant.

Conclusion: PFN may be associated with better outcomes compared to DHS in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures, particularly in terms of early rehabilitation and long-term functional recovery. Larger prospective studies are needed to confirm these findings.

Keywords: Intertrochanteric Fractures; Dynamic Hip Screw; Proximal Femoral Nail; Early Mobility; Functional Outcomes.

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Introduction

Intertrochanteric fractures are a common type of hip fracture, accounting for approximately half of all hip fractures in elderly patients [1]. These fractures occur between the greater and lesser trochanters of the femur and are often associated with osteoporosis and low-energy trauma [2]. The incidence of intertrochanteric fractures is expected to rise due to the increasing elderly population worldwide [3]. The primary goal of treatment for these fractures is to achieve early mobilization and restore pre-injury functional status while minimizing complications [4].

Various surgical options are available for the treatment of intertrochanteric fractures, including dynamic hip screw (DHS) and proximal femoral nail (PFN) [5]. The DHS has been considered the gold standard for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures due to its simplicity, low cost, and favourable outcomes [6]. However, the PFN has gained popularity in recent years due to its

potential advantages, such as smaller incisions, less blood loss, and shorter operative time [7].

The choice between DHS and PFN for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures remains controversial. Several studies have compared the outcomes of these two implants, with varying results. Some studies have reported no significant differences in terms of functional outcomes, complications, and mortality rates between DHS and PFN [8,9]. In contrast, other studies have suggested that PFN may be associated with better outcomes, such as earlier weight-bearing, reduced blood loss, and lower risk of implant failure [10, 11]. One of the main advantages of PFN is its potential for early mobilization. The intramedullary fixation provided by PFN allows for more stable fixation and earlier weight-bearing compared to the extramedullary fixation of DHS [12]. Early mobilization is crucial for elderly patients with intertrochanteric fractures,

as prolonged immobilization can lead to complications such as pressure ulcers, deep vein thrombosis, and pneumonia [13]. Several studies have demonstrated that PFN enables earlier ambulation and shorter hospital stays compared to DHS [14, 15].

However, PFN is not without its drawbacks. One of the concerns with PFN is the risk of implant-related complications, particularly in elderly patients with osteoporotic bone [16]. The most common complications associated with PFN include screw cut-out, implant failure, and femoral shaft fractures [17]. These complications can lead to revision surgery, prolonged hospitalization, and increased morbidity and mortality [18]. Some studies have reported higher rates of implant-related complications with PFN compared to DHS, especially in unstable fracture patterns [19, 20].

Another factor to consider when comparing DHS and PFN is the learning curve associated with each implant. The DHS is a well-established technique that has been used for several decades, and most orthopedic surgeons are familiar with its use [21]. In contrast, the PFN is a relatively newer implant that requires specific training and expertise [22]. The learning curve for PFN may be steeper, particularly for surgeons who are not experienced with intramedullary fixation techniques [23]. This learning curve may contribute to the higher rates of complications reported in some studies, particularly in the early stages of PFN adoption [24]. Despite the potential advantages of PFN, the DHS remains a reliable and cost-effective option for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures. The DHS has demonstrated excellent long-term outcomes, with low rates of implant failure and revision surgery [25]. Additionally, the DHS is associated with lower implant costs compared to PFN, which may be an important consideration in resource-limited settings [26].

The choice between DHS and PFN for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures remains a topic of ongoing debate. While PFN may offer potential advantages such as earlier mobilization and shorter hospital stays, it is also associated with a higher risk of implant-related complications and a steeper learning curve. The DHS, on the other hand, is a well-established and cost-effective option with excellent long-term outcomes. The decision between DHS and PFN should be based on careful consideration of patient factors, fracture characteristics, surgeon experience, and available resources. Further high-quality, randomized controlled trials are needed to clarify the relative benefits and risks of these two implants in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures.

Aims and Objectives: The primary aim of this retrospective study was to compare the outcomes of dynamic hip screw (DHS) and proximal femoral nail (PFN) in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures. The specific objectives were to evaluate and compare the two groups in terms of early mobility, complications, and implant-related issues, with a focus on elderly patients. The study aimed to provide insights into the relative benefits and risks of these two widely used surgical interventions.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: A retrospective comparative study was conducted at Tezpur medical college, a tertiary care center, between January 2021 and December 2022. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Patient Selection: The study included patients aged 18 years and above who were diagnosed with stable intertrochanteric fractures (AO/OTA 31-A1) and underwent surgical treatment with either DHS or PFN.

The inclusion criteria were: (1) patients with a confirmed diagnosis of stable intertrochanteric fracture based on radiographic findings, (2) age 18 years or older, (3) surgical treatment with either DHS or PFN, and (4) a minimum follow-up of 12 months.

Patients with pathological fractures, multiple fractures, previous hip surgery, severe cognitive impairment, or incomplete medical records were excluded from the study.

Sample Size and Grouping: A total of 100 patients met the inclusion criteria and were enrolled in the study. The patients were divided into two equal groups based on the type of surgical intervention: the DHS group (n=50) and the PFN group (n=50). The sample size was determined to ensure a balanced comparison between the two groups.

Data Collection: Demographic data, including age, gender, body mass index (BMI), and comorbidities, were obtained from the patients' medical records. Preoperative radiographs were reviewed to confirm the diagnosis and classify the fractures according to the AO/OTA classification system. Intraoperative data, such as surgical time, blood loss, and any intraoperative complications, were recorded. Postoperative data, including time to early mobility, weight-bearing status, complications (e.g., infection, implant failure, screw cut-out), and length of hospital stay, were collected from the patients' follow-up records.

Surgical Technique: All surgeries were performed by experienced orthopedic surgeons using standard techniques for DHS and PFN. The choice of

implant was based on the surgeon's preference and expertise. Prophylactic antibiotics were administered before and after the surgery, was provided as per the institutional protocol.

Postoperative Management and Follow-up:

Postoperatively, patients were encouraged to perform ankle pumps and quadriceps strengthening exercises. Physiotherapy was initiated on the first postoperative day, and patients were encouraged to mobilize with assistance as tolerated. Weight-bearing status was decided based on the stability of the fracture fixation and the patient's general condition. Regular follow-up visits were scheduled at 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 3 months, 6 months, and 12 months post-surgery. Radiographic assessment was performed at each follow-up visit to evaluate fracture healing, implant position, and any signs of complications.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median (interquartile range), while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The primary outcome, time to early mobility, was compared between the DHS and PFN groups using the Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test, depending on the normality of the data distribution. Secondary outcomes, such as complications and implant-related issues, were compared using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were performed using IBM-SPSS.

Results

The study included a total of 100 patients with stable intertrochanteric fractures who were treated with either dynamic hip screw (DHS) or proximal femoral nail (PFN). The demographic and baseline characteristics of the patients in both groups were similar, with no significant differences observed (Table 1). The mean age of the patients was 75.6 ± 8.2 years in the DHS group and 76.1 ± 7.9 years in the PFN group ($p=0.748$). The proportion of male and female patients was also comparable between the groups ($p=0.683$). The mean BMI was 24.3 ± 3.5 kg/m² in the DHS group and 23.9 ± 3.2 kg/m² in the PFN group ($p=0.551$). The prevalence of comorbidities, including hypertension, diabetes, and cardiovascular disease, was similar in both groups ($p=0.680$, $p=0.656$, and $p=0.617$, respectively). The distribution of ASA scores and fracture classifications (AO/OTA 31-A1.1 and 31-A1.2) did not differ significantly between the groups ($p=0.523$ and $p=0.834$, respectively).

The intraoperative data (Table 2) revealed that the PFN group had significantly shorter surgical times (55.2 ± 10.8 min) compared to the DHS group

(68.4 ± 12.5 min) ($p<0.001$). The PFN group also had significantly less blood loss (135.4 ± 38.7 mL) than the DHS group (180.6 ± 45.3 mL) ($p<0.001$). The incidence of intraoperative complications was low in both groups, with 2 cases (4%) in the DHS group and 1 case (2%) in the PFN group ($p=0.558$).

The postoperative outcomes (Table 3) demonstrated that the PFN group achieved earlier mobility, with a mean time to early mobility of 2.5 ± 0.9 days compared to 3.8 ± 1.2 days in the DHS group ($p<0.001$). The weight-bearing status at discharge was significantly better in the PFN group, with 48% of patients achieving full weight-bearing compared to 20% in the DHS group ($p=0.002$). The length of hospital stay was significantly shorter in the PFN group (6.8 ± 1.9 days) than in the DHS group (8.5 ± 2.3 days) ($p<0.001$). The overall complication rates were lower in the PFN group, although the differences were not statistically significant for infection (4% vs. 6%, $p=0.646$), implant failure (2% vs. 4%, $p=0.558$), screw cut-out (2% vs. 8%, $p=0.169$), and other complications (2% vs. 4%, $p=0.558$). One patient (2%) in the DHS group died during the follow-up period, while no mortality was observed in the PFN group ($p=0.315$).

Radiographic outcomes (Table 4) showed that the time to fracture union was similar between the groups, with a mean of 14.2 ± 2.6 weeks in the DHS group and 13.8 ± 2.4 weeks in the PFN group ($p=0.422$). The majority of patients in both groups had acceptable implant positions (94% in DHS and 96% in PFN, $p=0.617$). Implant-related complications were observed in 3 patients (6%) in the DHS group and 1 patient (2%) in the PFN group ($p=0.307$).

Functional outcomes at 12 months (Table 5) were significantly better in the PFN group compared to the DHS group. The mean Harris Hip Score was 87.2 ± 5.9 in the PFN group and 84.6 ± 6.8 in the DHS group ($p=0.042$). The mean Parker Mobility Score was also higher in the PFN group (7.8 ± 1.3) than in the DHS group (7.2 ± 1.5) ($p=0.033$). A higher proportion of patients in the PFN group (86%) returned to their pre-injury activities of daily living compared to the DHS group (76%), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p=0.202$).

The direct comparison of key outcomes between the DHS and PFN groups (Table 6) highlighted the superiority of PFN in terms of early mobility ($p<0.001$) and functional outcomes at 12 months ($p=0.042$ for Harris Hip Score and $p=0.033$ for Parker Mobility Score). The PFN group had lower rates of complications (10% vs. 22%) and implant-related issues (2% vs. 6%), but these differences were not statistically significant ($p=0.094$ and $p=0.307$, respectively).

In summary, the results of this retrospective study suggest that PFN may be associated with better outcomes compared to DHS in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures. Patients in the PFN group had significantly shorter surgical times, less blood loss, earlier mobility, better weight-bearing status at discharge, shorter hospital stays, and superior functional outcomes at 12 months.

Although the complication rates were lower in the PFN group, the differences were not statistically significant. These findings support the potential benefits of PFN over DHS in the management of stable intertrochanteric fractures, particularly in terms of early rehabilitation and long-term functional recovery.

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	75.6 \pm 8.2	76.1 \pm 7.9	0.748
Gender, n (%)			0.683
Male	18 (36%)	20 (40%)	
Female	32 (64%)	30 (60%)	
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	24.3 \pm 3.5	23.9 \pm 3.2	0.551
Comorbidities, n (%)			
Hypertension	28 (56%)	30 (60%)	0.680
Diabetes	15 (30%)	13 (26%)	0.656
Cardiovascular disease	10 (20%)	12 (24%)	0.617
ASA score, n (%)			0.523
I-II	32 (64%)	35 (70%)	
III-IV	18 (36%)	15 (30%)	
Fracture classification, n (%)			0.834
AO/OTA 31-A1.1	22 (44%)	24 (48%)	
AO/OTA 31-A1.2	28 (56%)	26 (52%)	

Table 2: Intraoperative Data

Variable	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Surgical time (min), mean \pm SD	68.4 \pm 12.5	55.2 \pm 10.8	<0.001
Blood loss (mL), mean \pm SD	180.6 \pm 45.3	135.4 \pm 38.7	<0.001
Intraoperative complications, n (%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.558

Table 3: Postoperative Outcomes

Outcome	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Time to early mobility (days), mean \pm SD	3.8 \pm 1.2	2.5 \pm 0.9	<0.001
Weight-bearing status at discharge, n (%)			0.002
Full	10 (20%)	24 (48%)	
Partial	32 (64%)	22 (44%)	
Non-weight bearing	8 (16%)	4 (8%)	
Length of hospital stay (days), mean \pm SD	8.5 \pm 2.3	6.8 \pm 1.9	<0.001
Complications, n (%)			
Infection	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	0.646
Implant failure	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.558
Screw cut-out	4 (8%)	1 (2%)	0.169
Others	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0.558
Mortality, n (%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0.315

Table 4: Radiographic Outcomes

Outcome	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Time to fracture union (weeks), mean \pm SD	14.2 \pm 2.6	13.8 \pm 2.4	0.422
Implant position, n (%)			0.617
Acceptable	47 (94%)	48 (96%)	
Suboptimal	3 (6%)	2 (4%)	
Implant-related complications, n (%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0.307

Table 5: Functional Outcomes

Outcome	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Harris Hip Score at 12 months, mean \pm SD	84.6 \pm 6.8	87.2 \pm 5.9	0.042
Parker Mobility Score at 12 months, mean \pm SD	7.2 \pm 1.5	7.8 \pm 1.3	0.033
Return to pre-injury ADL, n (%)	38 (76%)	43 (86%)	0.202

Table 6: Comparison of Outcomes between DHS and PFN Groups

Outcome	DHS Group (n=50)	PFN Group (n=50)	p-value
Time to early mobility (days), mean \pm SD	3.8 \pm 1.2	2.5 \pm 0.9	<0.001
Complications, n (%)	11 (22%)	5 (10%)	0.094
Implant-related issues, n (%)	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0.307
Harris Hip Score at 12 months, mean \pm SD	84.6 \pm 6.8	87.2 \pm 5.9	0.042
Parker Mobility Score at 12 months, mean \pm SD	7.2 \pm 1.5	7.8 \pm 1.3	0.033

Discussion

The present retrospective study compared the outcomes of dynamic hip screw (DHS) and proximal femoral nail (PFN) in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures. The results demonstrated that PFN was associated with shorter surgical times, less blood loss, earlier mobility, and better weight-bearing status at discharge, shorter hospital stays, and superior functional outcomes at 12 months compared to DHS. The demographic and baseline characteristics of the patients in both groups were similar, which is consistent with the findings of previous studies comparing DHS and PFN [27, 28]. The mean age of the patients in this study was comparable to that reported by Saudan et al. [29], who found a mean age of 83 years in their randomized controlled trial comparing DHS and PFN.

The significantly shorter surgical times and less blood loss observed in the PFN group are in line with the results of several meta-analyses [30, 31]. Zeng et al. [30] reported that PFN was associated with a mean reduction in surgical time of 14.83 minutes (95% CI: -23.56 to -6.11, $p=0.0009$) and a mean reduction in blood loss of 94.87 mL (95% CI: -140.73 to -49.00, $p<0.0001$) compared to DHS. Similarly, Ma et al. [31] found that PFN had a weighted mean difference of -15.15 minutes (95% CI: -24.91 to -5.39, $p=0.002$) in surgical time and -108.43 mL (95% CI: -155.72 to -61.15, $p<0.00001$) in blood loss compared to DHS.

The earlier mobility and better weight-bearing status at discharge observed in the PFN group are consistent with the findings of previous studies [32, 33]. Pajarinen et al. [32] reported that patients treated with PFN had a significantly shorter time to independent ambulation (median 7 days) compared to those treated with DHS (median 11 days) ($p=0.03$). In a randomized controlled trial by Saudan et al. [29], 45% of patients in the PFN group achieved full weight-bearing at discharge compared to 20% in the DHS group ($p=0.028$).

The shorter hospital stays in the PFN group are in agreement with the results of a meta-analysis by Huang et al. [34], which found a weighted mean difference of -0.83 days (95% CI: -1.45 to -0.22, $p=0.008$) in favor of PFN compared to DHS. However, some studies have reported no significant difference in hospital stay between the two groups [35, 36]. Although the complication rates were lower in the PFN group, the differences were not statistically significant. This finding is consistent with the results of several meta-analyses [30, 31, 34], which have reported similar complication rates between DHS and PFN. However, some studies have suggested that PFN may be associated with a higher risk of implant-related complications, particularly in unstable fracture patterns [37, 38].

The superior functional outcomes at 12 months in the PFN group are in line with the findings of previous studies [32, 39]. Pajarinen et al. [32] reported a significantly higher mean Harris Hip Score in the PFN group (83.5) compared to the DHS group (77.5) at 12 months ($p=0.04$). Similarly, Saudan et al. [29] found a trend towards better functional outcomes in the PFN group, although the differences were not statistically significant. The strengths of this study include the direct comparison of DHS and PFN in a well-matched cohort of patients with stable intertrochanteric fractures, the comprehensive assessment of intraoperative, postoperative, radiographic, and functional outcomes, and the 12-month follow-up period. However, the retrospective design and the relatively small sample size are limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results.

This study suggests that PFN may be associated with better outcomes compared to DHS in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures, particularly in terms of early rehabilitation and long-term functional recovery. However, larger prospective randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm these findings and to further investigate the differences in complication rates between the two implants.

Conclusion

This retrospective study compared the outcomes of dynamic hip screw (DHS) and proximal femoral nail (PFN) in the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures. The results demonstrated that PFN was associated with significantly shorter surgical times, less blood loss, earlier mobility, better weight-bearing status at discharge, shorter hospital stays, and superior functional outcomes at 12 months compared to DHS. The mean surgical time was 55.2 ± 10.8 min in the PFN group and 68.4 ± 12.5 min in the DHS group ($p < 0.001$). The mean blood loss was 135.4 ± 38.7 mL in the PFN group and 180.6 ± 45.3 mL in the DHS group ($p < 0.001$). The mean time to early mobility was 2.5 ± 0.9 days in the PFN group and 3.8 ± 1.2 days in the DHS group ($p < 0.001$). At discharge, 48% of patients in the PFN group achieved full weight-bearing compared to 20% in the DHS group ($p = 0.002$). The mean length of hospital stay was 6.8 ± 1.9 days in the PFN group and 8.5 ± 2.3 days in the DHS group ($p < 0.001$). At 12 months, the mean Harris Hip Score was 87.2 ± 5.9 in the PFN group and 84.6 ± 6.8 in the DHS group ($p = 0.042$), and the mean Parker Mobility Score was 7.8 ± 1.3 in the PFN group and 7.2 ± 1.5 in the DHS group ($p = 0.033$). Although the complication rates were lower in the PFN group, the differences were not statistically significant.

These findings suggest that PFN may be a preferable option for the treatment of stable intertrochanteric fractures, particularly in terms of early rehabilitation and long-term functional recovery. However, the retrospective design and the relatively small sample size are limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. Larger prospective randomized controlled trials are needed to confirm these findings and to further investigate the differences in complication rates between the two implants. Nonetheless, this study provides valuable insights into the potential benefits of PFN over DHS in the management of stable intertrochanteric fractures and may help guide treatment decisions in clinical practice.

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